

DEVELOPMENT OF THE METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES FOR THE ATTITUDE CONTROL SYSTEM OF THE EARTH REMOTE SENSING SATELLITE IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE ONBOARD EQUIPMENT PARTIAL FAILURES

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Abstract

The spacecraft controllability of the angular motion is possible only with operability of the attitude and orbit control system (AOCS) of the spacecraft, sensors, actuators and the spacecraft power system. However, there is a rather significant probability of failure of this equipment during the operation of the spacecraft. This is especially observed after half of the spacecraft's lifetime or because of emergency situations. There is a problem which is connected with providing the maximum performance of the AOCS in case of partial failures of their actuators (reaction wheels (RW), magnetorquer rods (MGTR), etc.).

Thus, the purpose of this work is the development and synthesis of special algorithms for spacecraft angular motion control in the emergency situations which are connected with RWs partial failures and restrictions of onboard electricity consumption. The approach of synthesis of this control algorithms is based on using mobile control methods which allow to reserve RWs by MGTRs. There are different variants of control loops depending on MGTRs turning on combinations. There were proposed two types of control switching functions: time-periodic and switching by deviation. Also was proposed a methodology of controller synthesis using these switching functions.

Using this methodology and computer simulation, it was shown the possibility of providing angular nadir orientation and stabilization of the spacecraft with maximum 1–1.5 deg error in case of time-periodic switching functions implementation. Switching by deviation allows to reduce onboard electricity consumption for 25–30 % comparing with using time-periodic switching. However, the accuracy of stabilization significantly lower in case of switching by deviation. Considering these estimates, the corresponding methodological recommendations were formulated for use switching functions depending on emergency.

Keywords: attitude and orbit control system, actuators partial failures, energy saving.

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1. Introduction

Providing controllability of the angular position and targeting for the Earth remote sensing satellite is one of the key requirements for its normal functioning. To achieve this, the spacecraft is equipped by different actuators and sensors, such as sun sensors (SS), star trackers (ST), fiber optic gyroscopes (FOG), reaction wheels (RW), magnetorquer rods (MGTR), micro-propulsion jet systems (PS) and momentum wheels (MW). However, after a half of the lifespan, or as a result of emergency, there is a significant probability of incorrect operating of some actuators or even its failure. So, the methodology of failures determination in case of using pyramid RW scheme and configuration of the NASA standard of RW placement schemes has been proposed in the paper [1]. Authors proposed the methodological approach for RW failures diagnostic and determination the possibilities of optimal reserving or recovering of the failed RW. Using testbench were debugged special algorithms for testing, recovering or reserving the RW after failures [1]. Authors consider the possibility of RW recovering [1] and didn't take into account situation with fully failure RW. Also, nothing has been said about the possibility of duplicating a failed RW by another actuator (such as MGTR, micro chemical thruster, etc.).

Special algorithms that use MGTR's with other actuators and passive stabilization concepts had been considered in paper [2]. Therefore one of the options for such a combined use was the use of the RW in one channel instead of a MGTR (with the orthogonal arrangement of the RW along the three main axes of inertia of the spacecraft). This control algorithm is proposed to turn on the RW and MGTRs simultaneously [2]. In this case a control problem may arise due to the large difference between the torque generated by the RW's and MGTR's. Thus, when synthesizing controller, it is necessary to select gains considering the different magnitude of the control values in each channel. This obstacle greatly complicates the process of controller synthesis and can lead to loss of stability over the long intervals.

There are some limitations during spacecraft orientation with MGTRs control that can cause difficulties in control algorithms synthesis. The nature of the limitations is usually connected with:

- 1) cross-links in the control channels;
- 2) different frequency of changes in the projections of the magnetic induction vector of the Earth's magnetic field (EMF) on the body frame axes during flight (MGTR are usually arranged body frame axes);
- 3) problems in the gain selection when time-periodic changes of EMF induction vector.

However, the problem of the algorithm's development for the magnetic orientation and stabilization of satellites has a quite deep scientific study [3–10]. A time-periodic gain selection for synthesis magnetic controller was proposed in works [3, 4]. This approach allows to calculate gain of controller depending on the EMF induction projection change in each control channel during spacecraft orbiting. Also, this allows to increase the accuracy of control and optimize the control process by the minimization of magnetorquers activation [4]. However, from one hand, simulation results show a low performance of this controllers [4], on the other hand calculation of gain matrix (by solving the nonlinear algebraic Riccati equation) in each control sample can significantly overload on-board computer. The time-periodic linear-quadratic controllers are hard for implementation on the Earth remote sensing satellites due to specific of their work.

The theoretical study of three-axial spacecraft stabilization was carried out in the paper [5]. The angular velocity damping mode using «B-dot» algorithm is considered in this paper. There was determined controllability restrictions depending on orbit inclination. Thus, «B-dot» algorithm is not suitable for providing three axial orientation and spacecrafts angular maneuvers.

The robustness of the three-axial magnetic control was shown in the paper [6]. However, the control was analyzed during relatively short period of time, only 5400 s. Also, nothing was said about impact level of disturbing torques. In turn, the accuracy of three-axial stabilization using magnetorquers including influence of perturbation torques was determined in paper [7]. So, it was determined the decreasing of the accuracy stabilization with the increasing of orbit inclination to near polar orbits. It can be explained by near zero values of amplitude and low frequency of one of EMF induction projections on the Orbital Reference Frame of satellite during flight on near-polar orbits. Taking this into account, it is possible to make a control only based on the two remaining projections, which imposes additional restrictions of stabilization accuracy. Such an algorithm uses other actuators concurrently with magnetorquers with difficulties.

Thus, the sliding mode controller allows to use magnetorquers with other actuators concurrently [8]. This is explained by use special architecture that includes two parts: continues and switching [8]. A similar approach is used in mobile control methods [9, 10]. So, the mobile control method which is based on time-periodic switch functions is described in monograph [9]. In this case, the control loops are switched alternately at the regular intervals. At the same time, the control accuracy, in addition to the gain selection, is regulated by the choice of the interval length of each control loop operation and the switching frequency. Also, in article [10], a variant of the switching function synthesis is given, which is triggered depending on the specified maximum deviation of the angle values in each channel.

Thus, based on mobile control methods it has been proposed a new AOCS algorithm of the spacecraft with the combined use of the RWs and MGTRs, which allows to maintain its performance in emergency situations.

The problem of RW and MGTR concurred usage is in the different amount of the torque generated by these actuators. Taking into account the different magnitudes and frequencies in changing of EMF induction vector projections in each channel [11], this problem can add unstable control zones during flight. So, in case of near zero values of EMF induction vector projections in any channels (except RW channels) the controllability of the spacecraft can be lost. Thus, there are orbits with projections of the EMF induction vector on ORF axes that have near-zero values over most of the orbit. These orbits are usually near-polar Sun-synchronous orbits for Earth remote sensing satellites. The 3-axis stabilization of SC is uncontrollable or difficultly controllable on these orbits. The RWs are used usually for 3-axis SC stabilization and orientation on these orbits.

However, some RWs can be failed in emergency. On the other hand, if the SC is in the electricity restriction mode (particularly failures of solar panels, accumulators, etc.) then RW can't apply full performance to provide stabilization because of significant energy consumption.

Taking these aspects into account the purpose of the paper is the analysis of AOCS possibility to reserve RW by MGTR in emergency for providing 3-axis stabilization. This study considers the basic SC layout with three orthogonal RW to each other, located along the main SC axes of inertia.

Three types of emergency can be determined in this case:

- 1) One RW failure.
- 2) Two RWs failure.
- 3) Electricity restriction mode.

Therefore, to achieve the purpose of the research the following tasks has been formulated:

- 1) To determine the possibility of reserving RWs by MGTRs depend on the orbit and SC parameters, and formulate the methodology of synthesis of mobile control switching algorithms.
- 2) Performance analysis of spacecraft nadir pointing control and accuracy in case one RW will failure.
- 3) Accuracy analysis of spacecraft nadir pointing in case of one or two RWs failure.
- 4) Features analysis of nadir orientation maintenance in case of onboard electricity consumption restrictions.

2. Material and methods

2. 1. Coordinate systems

Fourth coordinate systems are used for modeling the orbital and attitude motion of the spacecraft (SC):

1) Earth-centered inertial J2000 reference frame (ECI). The origin of is placed in the Earth's center. Z -axis is directed normally to the mean equatorial plane, pointing towards the Northern Hemisphere, X -axis is the vector pointing from the center of the Earth to the mean vernal equinox. Y -axis: vector perpendicular to the X - and Z -axes, forming a right-handed coordinate system [11].

2) WGS-84 reference frame. The origin of is placed in the Earth's center. Z -axis is directed normally to the mean equatorial plane, pointing towards the Northern Hemisphere X -axis is the vector pointing from the center of the Earth to the point of intersection of the equator and the Greenwich meridian. Y -axis: vector perpendicular to the X - and Z -axes, forming a right-handed coordinate system [12].

3) Orbital reference frame (ORF). The origin (point O_1) is placed in the SC center of mass. X -axis is directed tangentially to the orbit and makes an acute angle with the velocity vector, Z -axis is directed to the Earth center, Y -axis is the vector perpendicular to the X - and Z -axes, forming a right-handed coordinate system [13].

4) Body fixed reference frame (BFRF). The origin (point O_2) is placed in the SC center of mass. The BFRF axes are co-directed with the main axes of inertia of the spacecraft.

2. 2. Mathematical model of orbital and attitude motion

The mathematical model of orbital motion in osculating elements for near-circular orbits is used for computer modeling of spacecraft motion. It can be written in the following form [14]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dh}{dt} &= \frac{h^2}{\xi} \cdot T, \\ \frac{de_x}{dt} &= h \cdot \left[S \cdot \sin F + T \cdot [(\xi + 1) \cdot \cos F + e_x] - W \cdot e_y \frac{\eta}{\xi} \right], \\ \frac{de_y}{dt} &= h \cdot \left[-S \cdot \cos F + T \cdot [(\xi + 1) \cdot \sin F + e_y] + W \cdot e_x \frac{\eta}{\xi} \right], \\ \frac{di_x}{dt} &= \frac{h \cdot \tilde{\varphi}}{2\xi} W \cdot \cos F, \quad \frac{di_y}{dt} = \frac{h \cdot \tilde{\varphi}}{2\xi} W \cdot \sin F, \quad \frac{dF}{dt} = \frac{\xi^2}{h^3 \mu} + W \cdot h \cdot \eta, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $e_x = e \cdot \cos(\omega + \Omega)$ (e is the eccentricity of the SC orbit; i is the SC orbit inclination; Ω is the argument of the ascending node; ω is the argument of perigee);

$$e_y = e \cdot \sin(\omega + \Omega); \quad i_x = \operatorname{tg}\left(\frac{i}{2}\right) \cdot \cos \Omega; \quad i_y = \operatorname{tg}\left(\frac{i}{2}\right) \cdot \sin \Omega; \quad h = \sqrt{\frac{p}{\mu}};$$

p is the focal parameter;

$$F = \omega + \Omega + \vartheta;$$

ϑ is the truth anomaly;

$$\xi = 1 + e_x \cos F + e_y \sin F; \quad \eta = i_x \sin F - i_y \cos F; \quad \tilde{\varphi} = 1 + i_x^2 + i_y^2;$$

t is the time of SC orbital motion; S , T , W are the projections of radial, transverse and normal perturbing accelerations on the ORF axes, respectively.

Gravitational, aerodynamic and solar pressure perturbations are taken into account in orbital motion model (1). To calculate the perturbative accelerations which are generated by these perturbations' algorithms [11, 13] are used in the modeling. The model of ECSS atmosphere standard [15] in the middle solar activity is used for calculations of the aerodynamic perturbations. The WMM2020 [12] model of Earth magnetic field is used in the research.

Attitude SC motion is presented by Euler dynamic equations and quaternion kinematic equations [16] in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} J \frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}}{dt} + \boldsymbol{\omega} \times (J \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \mathbf{M}^{cm} + \mathbf{M}^p, \quad (2) \\ \begin{bmatrix} \frac{dq_0}{dt} \\ \frac{dq_1}{dt} \\ \frac{dq_2}{dt} \\ \frac{dq_3}{dt} \end{bmatrix} &= 0.5 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega_x & -\omega_y & -\omega_z \\ \omega_x & 0 & \omega_z & -\omega_y \\ \omega_y & -\omega_z & 0 & \omega_x \\ \omega_z & \omega_y & -\omega_x & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} q_0 \\ q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where J is spacecraft tensor of inertia; $\boldsymbol{\omega} = [\omega_x \quad \omega_y \quad \omega_z]^T$ is angular velocity vector in BFRF; $\mathbf{M}^{cm} = [M_x^{cm} \quad M_y^{cm} \quad M_z^{cm}]^T$ is magnetic control torque vector in BFRF; $\mathbf{M}^p = [M_x^p \quad M_y^p \quad M_z^p]^T$ is a sum of perturbation torque (aerodynamic torque, gravitational torque, solar pressure torque) in BFRF; q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3 are the quaternion components in BFRF.

The methodology of calculation of aerodynamic, gravitational, solar pressure torques in ref. [13] is used to model perturbative torques. Transition between quaternion and roll, pitch, yaw angles is realized by algorithm [16].

2.3 PD-controller description

PD-controller architecture with pole placement gain selection is described in the ref. [10, 17]. Taking into account usage quaternion equation instead of Euler angles PD-controller [10, 17] control law will be written in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} M_x^c &= -J_{xx}(K_1\Delta\omega_x + K_2\Delta q_1), \\ M_y^c &= -J_{yy}(K_1\Delta\omega_y + K_2\Delta q_2), \\ M_z^c &= -J_{zz}(K_1\Delta\omega_z + K_2\Delta q_3), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where M_x^c , M_y^c , M_z^c are estimated PD-controller torques which are needed for determination control dipole magnetic moments; J_{xx}, J_{yy}, J_{zz} are the principal moments of the SC inertia; $\Delta\omega_x, \Delta\omega_y, \Delta\omega_z$ are the angular velocity mismatches; $\Delta q_1, \Delta q_2, \Delta q_3$ are the quaternion mismatches; K_1, K_2 are the gain coefficients.

In turn, gain coefficients are selected using Butterworth distribution formulas [18]:

$$K_1 = 1.4\omega_0, \quad K_2 = \omega_0^2, \quad (5)$$

where ω_0 is controller performance value.

2.4. Switching mobile control algorithms

Magnetic control torque can be written as:

$$M^{cm} = m \times B, \quad (6)$$

where $m = [m_x \ m_y \ m_z]^T$ is the vector of magnetic dipole moments which are generated by MGTR coils during control process in BFRF; $B = [B_x \ B_y \ B_z]^T$ is EMF induction vector in BFRF; \times is cross-product operator.

There are 6 variants of mobile control loops algorithms depend on type of the MGTR coils activation described in [9]. Using PD-controller algorithms (4), (5) these control loops can be presented in the following form:

1) Two coils are activated in each loop (when the single RW is operating):

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{cm} &= \text{sgn}(m_y) \cdot m_y \cdot B_z \Leftarrow m_y = \frac{M_x^c}{B_z} \\ M_y^{cm} &= -\text{sgn}(m_x) \cdot m_x \cdot B_z \Leftarrow m_x = -\frac{M_y^c}{B_z} \\ M_z^{cm} &= \text{sgn}(m_x) \cdot m_x \cdot B_y - \text{sgn}(m_y) \cdot m_y \cdot B_x \Leftarrow m_x = \frac{M_z^c}{B_y}, m_y = -\frac{M_z^c}{B_x} \end{aligned} \right\} \rightarrow \text{loop-I,} \\ \\ \left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{cm} &= -\text{sgn}(m_z) \cdot m_z \cdot B_y \Leftarrow m_z = -\frac{M_x^c}{B_y} \\ M_y^{cm} &= \text{sgn}(m_z) \cdot m_z \cdot B_x - \text{sgn}(m_x) \cdot m_x \cdot B_z \Leftarrow m_z = \frac{M_y^c}{B_x}, m_x = -\frac{M_y^c}{B_z} \\ M_z^{cm} &= \text{sgn}(m_x) \cdot m_x \cdot B_y \Leftarrow m_x = \frac{M_z^c}{B_y} \end{aligned} \right\} \rightarrow \text{loop-II,} \\ \\ \left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{cm} &= \text{sgn}(m_y) \cdot m_y \cdot B_z - \text{sgn}(m_z) \cdot m_z \cdot B_y \Leftarrow m_y = \frac{M_x^c}{B_z}, m_z = -\frac{M_x^c}{B_y} \\ M_y^{cm} &= \text{sgn}(m_z) \cdot m_z \cdot B_x \Leftarrow m_z = \frac{M_y^c}{B_x} \\ M_z^{cm} &= -\text{sgn}(m_y) \cdot m_y \cdot B_x \Leftarrow m_y = -\frac{M_z^c}{B_x} \end{aligned} \right\} \rightarrow \text{loop-III.} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

Depending on EMF induction vector changing during SC flight in the certain orbit two values of magnetic dipoles moments in each loop can be calculated using one of the two projections of B . Usually, the bigger value from two B projections is used for each magnetic dipole estimation in each loop.

In case of using single RW (two others RWs are failed) and loop with two coils (7) in general there are 9 variants of control switch algorithms with two loops when RW is in the first control loop and two coils are in the second. These variants of control algorithms can be presented in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{RW} = M_x^c \Leftarrow M_x^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-III} \\ m_z, m_y - \text{estimated using projection } B_x \end{aligned} \right\} -1, \\
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{RW} = M_x^c \Leftarrow M_x^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-II} \\ m_x, m_z - \text{estimated using projections } B_x, B_y \end{aligned} \right\} -2, \\
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{RW} = M_x^c \Leftarrow M_x^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-I} \\ m_x, m_y - \text{estimated using projections } B_z, B_x \end{aligned} \right\} -3, \\
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_y^{RW} = M_y^c \Leftarrow M_y^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-III} \\ m_z, m_y - \text{estimated using projections } B_y, B_x \end{aligned} \right\} -4, \\
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_y^{RW} = M_y^c \Leftarrow M_y^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-II} \\ m_z, m_x - \text{estimated using projection } B_y \end{aligned} \right\} -5, \\
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_y^{RW} = M_y^c \Leftarrow M_y^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-I} \\ m_y, m_x - \text{estimated using projections } B_z, B_y \end{aligned} \right\} -6, \\
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_z^{RW} = M_z^c \Leftarrow M_z^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-III} \\ m_y, m_z - \text{estimated using projections } B_z, B_x \end{aligned} \right\} -7, \\
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_z^{RW} = M_z^c \Leftarrow M_z^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-II} \\ m_z, m_x - \text{estimated using projections } B_y, B_z \end{aligned} \right\} -8, \\
 & \left. \begin{aligned} M_z^{RW} = M_z^c \Leftarrow M_z^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \text{ with loop-I} \\ m_y, m_x - \text{estimated using projections } B_z \end{aligned} \right\} -9, \tag{8}
 \end{aligned}$$

where M_x^{RW} , M_y^{RW} , M_z^{RW} are the control torques which are generated by RWs; M_{\max}^{RW} is the maximum value of the torque which can be generated by RWs.

«Switch» function for switching loops and RWs can be synthesized using deflection control principle [10, 19] or time-ordered switch functions [9] depending on performance and accuracy of control. Also, the methodology of synthesis of these switching algorithms includes next steps in the following order:

- 1-st step: Determination of SC orbital parameters and motion characteristics;
- 2-nd step: Estimation of the EMF induction vector projections changing periodicity in ORF during orbiting;
- 3-rd step: Failure type determination (number of failed RWs, testing onboard energy system, testing MGTR system);
- 4-th step: Determination of the required type of the SC orientation and stabilization (nadir, sun acquisition, target tracking, etc.);
- 5-th step: Selection of the most suitable control case (8) which can allow to achieve required SC orientation;
- 6-th step: Synthesis of switch function between RWs loop and magnetic loop (7) using approach [10, 19] or [9];
- 7-th step: Gain selection and analysis of the control stability.

An example of the type of synthesis of such a «switch» function will be given in the «Simulation results» section.

2) One coil is activated in each loop (when 2 from 3 RWs are operating):

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{cm} &= 0 \\ M_y^{cm} &= -\operatorname{sgn}(m_x) \cdot m_x \cdot B_z \Leftarrow m_x = -\frac{M_y^c}{B_z} \\ M_z^{cm} &= \operatorname{sgn}(m_x) \cdot m_x \cdot B_y \Leftarrow m_x = \frac{M_z^c}{B_y} \end{aligned} \right\} \rightarrow \text{loop-IV},$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{cm} &= -\operatorname{sgn}(m_z) \cdot m_z \cdot B_y \Leftarrow m_z = -\frac{M_x^c}{B_y} \\ M_y^{cm} &= \operatorname{sgn}(m_z) \cdot m_z \cdot B_x \Leftarrow m_z = \frac{M_y^c}{B_x} \\ M_z^{cm} &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \rightarrow \text{loop-V},$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{cm} &= \operatorname{sgn}(m_y) \cdot m_y \cdot B_z \Leftarrow m_y = \frac{M_x^c}{B_z} \\ M_y^{cm} &= 0 \\ M_z^{cm} &= -\operatorname{sgn}(m_y) \cdot m_y \cdot B_x \Leftarrow m_y = -\frac{M_z^c}{B_x} \end{aligned} \right\} \rightarrow \text{loop-VI}. \quad (9)$$

In this case, 2 types of algorithms for combined operation of RWs and MGTRs coils can be considered:

- 1) dual-loop mode, where two RWs operate concurrently in one loop, and one coil in the other;
- 2) three-loop mode, where two RWs operates, each of them has own separate loop and coil operates in the third loop.

Taking this approach into account there are 12 variants of control (6 variants with dual-mode loop and 6 variants with three-loop mode). These control variants can be written in follow form:

Dual - loop mode

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{RW} = M_x^c \Leftarrow M_x^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ M_y^{RW} = M_y^c \Leftarrow M_y^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ m_x - \text{estimated using projection } B_y \end{aligned} \right\} \text{with loop-VI} \left\{ \begin{aligned} M_x^{RW} = M_x^c \Leftarrow M_x^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ M_y^{RW} = M_y^c \Leftarrow M_y^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ m_y - \text{estimated using projection } B_x \end{aligned} \right\} \text{with loop-VI} \left. \right\} -2,$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_x^{RW} = M_x^c \Leftarrow M_x^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ M_z^{RW} = M_z^c \Leftarrow M_z^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ m_x - \text{estimated using projection } B_z \end{aligned} \right\} \text{with loop-IV} \left\{ \begin{aligned} M_x^{RW} = M_x^c \Leftarrow M_x^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ M_z^{RW} = M_z^c \Leftarrow M_z^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ m_z - \text{estimated using projection } B_x \end{aligned} \right\} \text{with loop-V} \left. \right\} -4,$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_y^{RW} = M_y^c \Leftarrow M_y^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ M_z^{RW} = M_z^c \Leftarrow M_z^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ m_z - \text{estimated using projection } B_y \end{aligned} \right\} \text{with loop-V} \left\{ \begin{aligned} M_y^{RW} = M_y^c \Leftarrow M_y^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ M_z^{RW} = M_z^c \Leftarrow M_z^c \leq M_{\max}^{RW} \\ m_y - \text{estimated using projection } B_z \end{aligned} \right\} \text{with loop-VI} \left. \right\} -6,$$

Three - loop mode

variants 7 – 12 have the same algorithms as 1 – 6, but RW operate in separate loops (1 RW – 1 loop). (10)

Synthesis of the «switch» function is based on the principle which presented in the previous item.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Simulation results

To analyze the efficiency of the developed stabilization algorithms using orbital and attitude motion models (1)–(3), control algorithms (4)–(10), it is proposed to carry out computer simulation for a spacecraft with the following parameters (Tables 1–3).

Time of flight simulation is 24 hours.

Table 1

Spacecraft mass, geometrical and magnetic parameters

Parameter	Value
Mass, kg	150
Cross-section area, m ²	0.61
Center of pressure offset, m	0.23
Maximum value of coil magnetic dipole moment, Am ²	15
Maximum torque value of RW, Nm	0.06

Table 2

Spacecraft tensor of inertia parameters

Tensor of inertia element, kg·m ²	Value
J_{xx}	15
J_{yy}	10
J_{zz}	20
J_{xy}	0.015
J_{xz}	0.042
J_{yz}	0.033

Table 3

Spacecraft orbit parameters

Parameter	Value
Semi-major axis, m	7006030.15
Eccentricity	0.002
Inclination, °	99

At the first step, let's analyze the SC orbital motion and change in the Earth's magnetic field for a given orientation (ideal situation when BFRF coincides with ORF – providing nadir pointing) when the spacecraft is orbiting throughout the day. The dynamic of orbital parameters changes during SC orbiting is shown on **Fig. 1**.

The dynamics of changes in the projections of the EMF induction vector on the ORF axes during SC orbiting is shown on **Fig. 2**.

Analyzing obtained results (**Fig. 1**) it can be concluded that satellite has perturbative orbit. Zonal, tesseral and sectoral harmonics of gravitational potential are taken into account.

Based on the analysis of the dynamics of changes in the Earth's magnetic field during SC orbiting (orbit with params in **Table 3**), it can be concluded that the EMF magnetic induction vector projection B_x has the greatest amplitude. This average value of B_x amplitude approximately has next ratio with amplitudes of B_y and B_z projections: $B_{x,max} \approx 2B_{y,max} \approx 4B_{z,max}$ (**Fig. 1**). Therefore, is the most expedient to build magnetic control according to projection B_x and B_y if it is possible.

Fig. 1. The dynamic of orbital parameters changes during SC orbiting

Fig. 2. Dynamics of changes in the projections of the Earth magnetic field induction vector on the orbital reference frame axes during spacecraft orbiting

Consider an example in the 1-st variant of emergency (task 2). Let the first RW failed in channel x , $M_x^{RW} = 0$. In turn, let there be a requirement to ensure the most accurate orientation in the nadir for the general imaging of the Earth's surface. To ensure controllability of SC in the emergency situation of this type, it is necessary to replace this RWs with an MGTRs. So, the largest control with the MGTR can be generated by using z -coil in the loop V (9). Thus, using the 5-th control variant in formula (10), considering the requirements of stabilization, two-loop control can be generated. Two-loop control is chosen to minimize the number of switching (in comparison with three-loop control) which can influence to control accuracy. Using time-periodic switching mobile control approach [9] «switch 1» function can be presented in follow form:

$$\text{switch 1} = \begin{cases} \text{loop-V, if } \Rightarrow 2k - 1 \leq T < 2k, \\ \left. \begin{matrix} M_y^{RW} \\ M_z^{RW} \end{matrix} \right\}, \text{if } \Rightarrow 2k \leq T < 2k + 2, \end{cases}$$

$$k = \frac{3}{2}, \frac{6}{2}, \frac{9}{2}, \dots, \frac{3n}{2},$$

$$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n_{end},$$

$$T_0 = 2, \tag{11}$$

where n is the number of control cycle; n_{end} is the number of the last control cycle; T is the time of controller (in seconds) with initial value T_0 .

Initial angles: $Roll = -60$ deg; $Pitch = -50$ deg; $Yaw = 70$ deg.

Initial angular velocities projections on BFRF respect to ORF: $\omega_x = 1.146$ deg/s; $\omega_y = -1.146$ deg/s; $\omega_z = 1.146$ deg/s.

The simulation results of SC (SC and orbit parameters are presented in **Tables 1–3**) orientation and stabilization using «switch 1» (11) during SC orbiting (simulation time – 1 day) are presented in the **Fig. 3, 4**. It can be concluded that for this SC in case of RW failed in the x -channel with reserving it by an electromagnet, it is possible to provide stabilization and orientation to nadir with a maximum error of 1.5 degrees in the pitch channel and 0.1 degrees in the yaw channel. The controller performance ω_0 is selected to the 0.08 for this variant of emergency. This accuracy of stabilization allows to provide general imaging without Earths terrain detailing.

Fig. 3. Three-axial spacecraft stabilization in emergency situation when reaction wheel failed in the x -channel

Fig. 4. Damping of initial angular velocities

Case 2 (Task 3). Let two RWs failed in the channels y and z ($M_z^{RW} = 0$ and $M_y^{RW} = 0$). Considering that the maximum MGTR control torque can be generated according to the EMF induction due to vector projection B_x , it is most expedient to use control variant 1 in (8). In this case z and y coils operate in the third loop concurrently and RW x in the second loop. So, the «switch 2» function can be written as:

$$\text{switch } 2 = \begin{cases} \text{loop-III, if } \Rightarrow 2k - 1 \leq T < 2k, \\ M_x^{RW}, \text{ if } \Rightarrow 2k \leq T < 2k + 2, \end{cases}$$

$$k = \frac{3}{2}, \frac{6}{2}, \frac{9}{2}, \dots, \frac{3n}{2},$$

$$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n_{end},$$

$$T_0 = 2. \tag{12}$$

Initial angles: $Roll = -70$ deg; $Pitch = 50$ deg; $Yaw = 60$ deg.

Initial angular velocities projections on BFRF respect to ORF: $\omega_x = 1.146$ deg/s; $\omega_y = -1.146$ deg/s; $\omega_z = 1.146$ deg/s.

Simulation results of the SC nadir orientation and stabilization in this type of emergency situation, using function «switch 2» (12) is presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Three-axial spacecraft stabilization in emergency situation when 2 RWs in x and y -channels are failed

So, in this situation, the maximum errors of the SC nadir orientation and stabilization are 0.2° in the roll channel, 0.01° in the pitch and yaw channels (Fig. 5). These accuracy errors of the SC orientation are much more less than errors obtained in case of only the 1 RW failure. Therefore, the reorientation time in the first case (Fig. 3) is less on 30 % in the second case (Fig. 5). However, when using 2 MGTRs and 1 RW, the onboard electricity consumption is 25 % less than using 2 RWs and 1 MGTR. The controller performance ω_0 is selected to 0.08 for this emergency. In turn, the controller has so good robustness in the first and second cases stabilizing and orienting satellite with initial angular velocities.

In the 3-rd case (Task 4) the emergency is connected with the SC onboard energy system particular failure what caused the deficit of onboard electricity. Also, there is not enough electricity for 3 RWs operation. Only one RW and MGTRs can be used.

Let it is required to ensure the maintenance of the SC rough stabilization, with a maximum error of no more than 15° in each channel. To meet this requirement, let choose the variant 1 in (8) when using M_x^{RW} (x -RW) and loop-III. Synthesis of «switch 3» function is proposed with using deflection control approach [18] in follow form:

$$\text{switch 3} = \begin{cases} \text{loop-III, activates if } ((pitch > pitch_{max}) \text{ and } \\ (yaw > yaw_{max})) \text{ or } (yaw > yaw_{max}) \text{ or} \\ (pitch > pitch_{max}), (roll < roll_{max}) \\ M_x^{RW}, \text{ activates if } (roll > roll_{max}), \\ 0, \text{ if } (roll < roll_{max}) \text{ and } (pitch < pitch_{max}) \text{ and } (yaw < yaw_{max}), \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where $roll_{max}$, $pitch_{max}$, yaw_{max} are maximum values in roll, pitch and yaw channels when activates «switch 3» for the loop transition. In turn transition between input $roll_{max}$, $pitch_{max}$, yaw_{max} parameters and quaternion in the model (3) is realized using methodology [16].

Simulation results of the SC stabilization using «switch 3» function is presented in Fig. 6.

This approach makes it possible to minimize the operating time of the RWs and MGTRs by turning on them only when a given deviation is reached. The maximum deviation in $roll_{max}$, $pitch_{max}$, yaw_{max} channels is 10° . In turn, the maximum error was 20° in the yaw channel. Considering such a short time of such an error, it can be considered a random short-time «jump» and not taken into account. Therefore, the rest of the values for all the channels fell into the specified range of 15° . Thus, according to the criteria [18], the stability of stabilization is ensured. The onboard energy consumption was 30 kJ, which is 30 % less than in the second variant (Fig. 5). Using this control law (13) the controller performance ω_0 is 0.04.

Fig. 6. Three-axis spacecraft rough stabilization due to electricity deficit with using x – reaction wheel and z, y – coils

3. 2. Discussion

The obtained results showed the possibility of using the duplication of RWs by MGTRs to ensure three-axis SC stabilization in the next emergency situations:

- 1) partial failure of the spacecraft power supply system, which leads to a deficit of onboard electricity;
- 2) failure of a part of the RW.

The proposed approaches (4)–(10) to the synthesis of such algorithms make it possible to create a methodology for choosing the required orientation and stabilization algorithm for the SC for a wide range of emergency situations when failed RWs can be reserved by MGTRs. Also, the proposed possible variants of the «mobile control» loops (8), (10) make it easier for various combinations of concurrent use of RWs and MGTRs to synthesize the «switch» functions based on the SC parameters and the orbit characteristics.

Using computer simulation, it has been shown the performance of «mobile control» synthesized algorithms in three types of emergency situations:

- 1) one from three RWs failure;
- 2) two from three RWs failure;
- 3) electricity consumption restriction.

In the first situation it has been obtained the highest performance of the magnetic control system (**Fig. 3, 4**). The transition process time was about 4000 s. It can be noted a rather high robustness of the system under the influence of perturbing aerodynamic torque, gravitational torque, sunlight pressure torque, as well as the initial rotation of the spacecraft. However, the accuracy of orientation and stabilization of the spacecraft came out with a periodically repeating pulsating error with averaged value of 1.0 degrees in pitch. This can be explained by the impact of cross-link perturbation in the loop with electromagnet and periodic pulse activation of 2 RWs. So, when the magnetorquer is activated, and the control is built along the y -projection of the EMF induction in the roll channel, a perturbation occurs in the pitch channel along the x -projection of EMF induction which has the highest amplitude (**Fig. 2**). Considering the off RWs in second loop at this time, it is the source of additional cyclic permanent error. Also, taking into account the symmetric gains of PD controller in each control loop a sharp jump in perturbation (which can be the resonance of different perturbations) does not have time to be fully compensated by the control system. This can also be an additional source of error. A possible solution to this is the development of the PD or PID controller with an asymmetrical choice of gain in the control channels. It can be the direction for future researchers.

In the second situation (**Fig. 5**) the control system has the same robustness as in the first case. In turn, the transition process time is low then in the first case. This is due to the greater use of the magnetic component in the control (2 channels, instead of one in the first case) and the lower speed of MGTRs orientation systems than RWs ones. The accuracy of stabilization is higher than in the first case. The smaller control error is explained by the smaller influence of perturbative magnetic cross-link in loop III (7) because of smaller amplitudes of EMF induction projections

in perturbative channel (y and z projection smaller than x (**Fig. 2**)). In turn in the second situation, it can be a worst case when $M_x^{RW} = 0$ and $M_y^{RW} = 0$. In this case, taking into account near zero values of B_z EMF induction projection (**Fig. 2**), reserving can be realized by using loop III (7), and control will calculate using B_x and B_y EMF induction projections. However, it will be two perturbative cross-links torquers in x and z channels.

Thus, the accuracy of stabilization depends on a certain combination of alternate switching on of the loops with RWs and loops with MGTRs. Taking this into account, in the practical implementation of such methods, it is necessary to carry out additional analysis of the stabilization accuracy using Monte Carlo statistical modeling methods and different scenarios.

It is also can be noted that when using two MGTRs and one RW, electricity consumption for providing control is about 20–25 % lower than when using two RWs and one MGTR. In turn, to ensure the maintenance of rough controllability of the satellite, a third variant of control by deviation is proposed (**Fig. 6**). So, in this case, controller is triggered only when certain threshold deviation values are reached in the roll, pitch and yaw channels, which minimize control [10, 19]. It can allow to reduce electricity consumption by 30 % less than in the second case or by 50–60 % than in the first. The disadvantage in this case is the loss of stabilization accuracy.

In turn, MGTRs and RWs have some peculiarities in practical usage. So, when using MGTRs there are some time delays between synthesis of program control torque and generation of real control torque. It can be explained by hysteresis influence during magnetic dipole torquer generations. The value of this delay depends on MGTR coils construction and material properties. Time delays between control signal and control torque generation are observed during RW usage too. The value of the time delay depends on the inertial characteristics of RW rotor and controller properties. Considering these, when analyzing the features of controlling the angular stabilization of a satellite using the proposed algorithms, it is necessary to take into account the influence of these time delays, as well as the noise of the measuring equipment. Also, to determine the full limits of the effective implementation of these algorithms in practice, it is necessary to test them for a wider range of satellite operation modes (for example Target Tracking sliding mode, Sun Tracking, etc.). This can be a further development of this research direction.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of AOCS possibility to provide 3-axial angular control in the case of reserve RWs by MGTRs in the emergency situations is carried out in the paper. Based on this analysis, the algorithms for controlling the angular motion of the spacecraft with the combined use of RWs and MGTRs to ensure orientation and stabilization have been developed. The methodological approaches of «switch» functions synthesis depending on the type of emergency situation have been developed using these control algorithms.

These developed algorithms and methodological approaches have been tested using computer simulation of SC orbital and attitude motion with providing nadir orientation. It has been shown that using these algorithms can provide 3-axial angular stabilization in emergency situations which are connected with deficit of onboard electricity and RWs failures.

Two approaches to the synthesis of switching control functions are proposed: switching by deviation and time-periodic switch functions. The highest accuracy of stabilization has been achieved using time-periodic switch functions. In turn, the influence of the inclusion of various combinations of control loops (2 RW's and 1 MGTR and 2 MGTR's and 1 RW) on the accuracy and speed of control system was determined.

The minimal onboard electricity consumption has been estimated when using switch functions which are based on switching by deviation. The use of this approach made it possible to reduce the onboard electricity consumption by 25–30 % compared to the use of time-periodic switching functions.

These results showed the possibility of a certain functioning of the SC AOCS in these emergency situations, which can expand the scope of spacecrafts operation in the case of partial failures of AOCS executive devices.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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